

Standard operating procedures for NMR sample shipment

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Procedures for sample shipment

Having reliable standard operating procedures for sample shipment is key for remote access. According to the surveys carried out in WP2 of the R-NMR project, most NMR facilities currently lack defined standard operating procedures for sample shipment and do not provide users with written instructions on how to package samples for shipment. Building on information collected in WP2, we provide below guidelines and flowcharts for sample shipment.

Shipping samples for solution NMR

Sample stability will determine the best state in which to ship a sample for solution NMR.

1) If the sample can be rapidly frozen and then thawed without damaging the material, then shipping the frozen sample in a small plastic (or glass) vial is probably the best method for sample shipment. The sample can be packed in dry ice for shipping. It is desirable that the solution already contains the necessary deuterated solvent for locking so that the only sample manipulation required at the remote NMR facility is to thaw the sample and transfer it to an NMR tube supplied by the user.

2) If the material can be lyophilized and redissolved without damaging the material then this is another good method for sample shipment. The remote user should provide appropriate buffer (containing deuterated solvent) to redissolve the material by facility staff once it has arrived at the remote facility. If adjustment of sample pH is required then this will need to be discussed with facility staff. Depending on the sample stability, the lyophilized powder can either be shipped in dry ice or at room temperature.

3) If the sample cannot be frozen or lyophilized then it will be necessary to ship the sample as a solution, ideally in an unbreakable tube/vial, at either ambient temperature or cooled (but not frozen). Shipment at ambient temperature is straightforward but may result in sample degradation. Shipment at cooler temperatures will be more difficult depending on the door-to-door shipment time. It is desirable that the solution already contains the necessary deuterated solvent for locking so that the only sample manipulation required at the NMR facility is to transfer it to an NMR tube supplied by the remote user.

4) Shipment of solution NMR samples in NMR tubes may be the least desirable method for shipment due to the fragile nature of NMR tubes, possible leakage of the sample at the cap/tube interface and the possible movement of the liquid along the NMR tube which may result in bubbles forming. However, this method of shipment may be necessary for air-sensitive samples placed in NMR tubes under controlled conditions.

5) Samples for metabolomic studies may need to be shipped to the NMR facility in a 'sealed' state so that no manipulation is done once they arrive. For facilities with sample changers, the samples may be put into 'short' NMR tubes loaded into the 96-tube racks with a top on the rack to hold the tubes in position. If possible, the rack should be kept upright during shipment. If the samples can be manipulated at the remote NMR facility, then it may be better to ship the samples in a frozen state and then transfer to tubes/racks at the facility.

6) At the end of the experiments, the samples are returned to the user in the form of a solution, either directly in the NMR tube with the associated risks mentioned above, or in an unbreakable tube/vial, at either ambient temperature or cooled.

The remote user should provide the following information with the sample that is shipped: Sample Name, Quantity/Concentration, Solvent composition (buffer type and pH, ionic strength, amount of deuterated solvent), Toxicity, Conditions for sample storage prior to NMR experiments.

Shipping samples for solid-state NMR

A variety of samples can be considered, from powdered materials to sedimented proteins or cell extracts.

1) Samples can be packed into solid-state NMR rotors by the remote user prior to shipment. This is possible if the remote user has the appropriate rotor in-house and the necessary tools to pack the rotor. The remote user should discuss appropriate rotors and rotor packing procedure with the NMR facility before preparing the sample.

2) Samples can be shipped and packed into the appropriate rotor at the NMR facility. This may be the preferred procedure at a facility if visual inspection of the material is required before packing the rotor. Samples can be shipped in dry ice, in a cold package or at room temperature.

3) Air sensitive samples require additional care. The samples will need to be placed in a sealed container under an inert atmosphere (oxygen free or other) prior to shipment and the NMR facility will need to have a glove box available to transfer the sample to a rotor. A rotor placed in a sealed container can also be directly shipped to the NMR facility.

4) At the end of the experiments, the samples are returned to the user, either directly in the NMR rotor or in their solid form, at ambient temperature or cooled.

The remote user should provide the following information with the sample that is shipped: Sample Name, Quantity/Concentration, Sample composition, Toxicity, Conditions for sample storage prior to NMR experiments.

Figure 1: Work flowchart for sample shipment.